

Representing the State-Of-The-Art Baseline

The single-sprint version of the linear programming model proposed by Golfarelli et al. [1, 2] serves as the state-of-the-art benchmark. The objective function of this model aims to maximize the cumulative business value of the user stories selected for the sprint. The business value of each story is increased if related (affine) stories are included in the same sprint or if the story is critical (i.e., urgent). Importantly, the objective function is fixed and does not account for team-specific contexts.

In their capacity constraint formulation, Golfarelli et al. increase the story points of user stories by their uncertainty risk. Similar to our dependency constraint, their model includes inequalities that ensure prerequisite stories for a given story are either completed beforehand or planned for the same sprint. Their model differentiates between AND-type and OR-type dependencies.

The single-sprint version of the linear programming model proposed by Golfarelli et al. defines the following variables:

Definition 1 (Sprint Planning Problem). Given a set of n user stories U in the backlog, let:

- $x_i = 1$ if and only if story i is included in the upcoming sprint, 0 otherwise;
- u_i be the utility (i.e., business value) of story i ;
- p_i be the number of story points of story i ;
- p^{max} be the capacity of the sprint (i.e., team velocity), measured in story points;
- r_i^{cr} be the criticality risk (i.e., urgency) of story i
- r_i^{un} be the uncertainty risk of story i ;
- a_i be the affinity of story i ;
- $Y_i \subset U$ be the set of stories related (affine) to story i ;
- y_i be an auxiliary variable related to the number of stories in Y_i included in the upcoming sprint. y_i is zero if story i is not part of the sprint, otherwise it equals the number of stories in Y_i that are included in the sprint;
- $D_i \subset U$ be the set of stories on which story i depends and that have not been completed yet;
- $U \supseteq U^{AND} \cup U^{OR}$, where U^{AND} and U^{OR} are the subsets of stories having dependency type *AND* and *OR*, respectively;

The sprint planning problem involves determining an optimal assignment of the x_i variables. The linear programming formulation proposed by Golfarelli et al. is as follows:

$$z = \text{Max} \sum_{i=1}^n u_i (r_i^{cr} x_i + a_i \frac{y_i}{|Y_i|}) \quad (1)$$

subject to constraints:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n p_i r_i^{un} x_i \leq p^{max} \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{j \in D_i} x_j \geq x_i \quad \forall i \in U^{OR} \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{j \in D_i} x_j \geq x_i |D_i| \quad \forall i \in U^{AND} \quad (4)$$

Translation to ING context

Golfarelli et al. use similar prioritization criteria but with different terminology. Specifically, their factors “utility” and “criticality” correspond to what we refer to as “business value” and “urgency.” Consequently, in the context of the ING data, we measure utility and criticality as business value and urgency, respectively. In adapting the linear programming formulation to the ING context, we make two modifications:

- We use our delay risk factor as a proxy for the “uncertainty risk” factor defined by Golfarelli et al. They describe an uncertain story as one whose complexity is hard to estimate due to potential unexpected problems, a phenomenon that corresponds with our delay risk factor.
- At ING, all dependencies are of the AND-type. Therefore, we exclude Equation 3, which handles OR-type dependencies, as it is not applicable in the ING context.

Consequently, we implement the linear programming formulation of Golfarelli et al. in the context of ING as follows:

$$z = \text{Max} \sum_{i=1}^n u_i (r_i^{cr} x_i + a_i \frac{y_i}{|Y_i|}) \quad (1)$$

subject to constraints:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n p_i r_i^{un} x_i \leq p^{max} \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{j \in D_i} x_j \geq x_i |D_i| \quad (3)$$

References

- [1] GOLFARELLI, M., RIZZI, S., AND TURRICCHIA, E. Sprint planning optimization in agile data warehouse design. In *Data Warehousing and Knowledge Discovery: 14th International Conference, DaWaK 2012, Vienna, Austria, September 3-6, 2012. Proceedings 14* (2012), Springer, pp. 30–41.
- [2] GOLFARELLI, M., RIZZI, S., AND TURRICCHIA, E. Multi-sprint planning and smooth replanning: An optimization model. *Journal of systems and software* 86, 9 (2013), 2357–2370.